

Is Peer Pressure A Negative Force On The Adolescent? The Case of Takoradi Technical University

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Doris Akua Boateng (Mrs)**-Administrator-University Hall-Takoradi Technical University

⁽²⁾ **Judith McClain-Afful**-Administrator-GetFund Hall-Takoradi Technical University

Abstract

Many times, peer pressure has been attributed to a negative force more especially amongst the adolescents. The issue lies with a traditional mindset, and a rigid concept that peer influence has limited producibility and their company is always perceived as tilted to social vices and immorality such theft, drug abuse sex and other nefarious activities. At the tertiary where the adolescent form over 80% of the student population and considered as mature and independent of forming their own opinions, the parent is still apprehensive about the kind of relationship and association their wards encounter or join. The tertiary institution is one stage of life of the adolescent where a lot of responsibilities can be instilled. There are amongst others social clubs, debate clubs, and forum for talents in leadership at the JCR level under the Students' Affairs Directorate headed by a Dean. These institutions tend to develop the total being of the student into productive elements later in life. Such students wield so much influence that they are able to command respect. It is therefore not out of place to make such students a conduit control and influence others. Yet the student front is heard only when there is bad news or mischief. The mode of data collection was a descriptive questionnaire. 200 males and females final year students were randomly selected. The reason being that having passed through the processes of tertiary education they must have been exposed to a varied of experiences in the university, and there is the certainty that they must have formed their identity. Responses, therefore, could be accurate.

Keywords: Peer pressure, adolescence, negative force

Introduction

Peer pressure means giving force to any activities: an influence of friends or each other and inducing change in the mental and emotional behaviour by the people belonging to the same group with similar interest, age background, and social status,(Weinfied, 2010). Peer pressure is the direct influence of people by peers, or the effect on an individual who gets encouraged to follow their peers by changing their attitudes, values or behaviour to conform to those of the influencing group or individual. It is normally linked with adolescence risk taking behaviour such as crime, drugs abuse and sexual behaviour. However, there are positive results associated with peer influence, for example marked an increase in achievement in academic or social work, (Kelie, 2013). Peer pressure can affect people of all race, ethnicity or age and with whom and what people encounter. But contrarily, the maximum result is for negative behaviour. Normally the student skips classes, steals and cheats, takes to drug or alcohol as a cause of peer pressure. Influences of peer maybe in all ages and places, such as in the workplace, in school, in society. Peer pressure tends to influence the group to litter in the street watch films, bunk class, lease other, steal and spoil public properties (Ariel, 2011).

The pressure nowadays is not only with face to face interaction with peers of people; the world of technology has brought interaction even in confines of one's room. Sometimes, one cannot only associate one's behaviour with whom a person interacts with since technology abounds with all kinds of information readily available with the click of the button. (Ariel, 2011)

Ms. Alorwu-Tay, Afadjato-South District Chief Executive at Volta Regional Girls' Vacation Camp at Have, on the theme *Empowering Girls towards improving Volta Region's performance in the Basic Education Certificate and Building the Potential for leadership*" against the backdrop of falling standards in the BECE in the last four years. (graphic.com.ghnewsgeneral) advised the girls to desist from peer pressure and indecent dressing under the pretext of modernity and civilization. One would have expected that having camped the girls for

coordination and group participation, the girls would have been advised to take advantage of the fraternity and help one another to learn and perform. It appears whenever adolescents meet, parents are always uncomfortable, and the clarion call is for them to resist negative influence.

Background

As a Hall Administrator, I encounter a lot of parents' concern about which roommates their children have to cope with. Some parents openly express their frustration by pleading that their children be in the company of good peers for roommates.

The University Hostel accommodates students of all background irrespective of race or colour. Most of them come straight after the Senior High School where they were usually under strict supervision.

The University is their first 'freedom' residence in terms of education. There is the likelihood that some students may take advantage of the 'freedom' to indulge themselves in what otherwise they need not. There is also the possibility that the student may carry on with the discipline instilled in them from the home and school. The concern is, most parents are always apprehensive about whom their children interact with because peers are perceived as a bad influence.

Problem Statement

Students who are mostly adolescents come face to face with choices as they struggle to take certain major decisions in their lives. The adolescence seems a period of great opportunity as it marks the time when the adolescent is equipped with the necessary skills and mind frame to meet society's expectation for adulthood.

In the ecological systems theory by Bronfenbrenner (1979) cited in Berk, (2000) adolescent acquire information that influences their decision-making from the parents, siblings, family members, teachers, religious bodies, media, and friends. Regardless of all these stakeholders involved with the development and choices of the adolescent, research findings indicate that peers have a more powerful influence on adolescents' decision-making (Oswald and Sons, 1998).

The word pressure tends to get a bad connotation but in general peer pressure can also be beneficial. While the majority have heard the 'don't give in to peers pressure,' little is heard about peers who urge their mates to join the debate and other positive responses because they have seen something good in the mates. Peers can be good when their pressure motivates them to achieve some wholesome goal. Regardless of how one is brought up, kids will likely continue to be pressured by other kids not because they mean any harm but because that is just how their social structure works. The outcome of the pressure sometimes depends on social, financial and cultural circumstance.

What is mind boggling is why the peer alone is pegged as pressure. Peers appear the domineering factor in the lives of the adolescents; meanwhile there are other stakeholders like the parents, academic institutions and sometimes the church in the development of the adolescent. If the adolescent has such domineering impact on their peers, then they can be made useful tools to shape the lives of one another.

This paper seeks to investigate if peers are always a 'powerful negative force.'

The objective of the study:

To ascertain whether peer pressure is always a negative influence

To identify areas where peers may influence their mates positively

To recommend areas where peers can be trained to reinforce the positive response

Peer pressure

Reason(1990) asserts that decision can be made under peer pressure without giving proper consideration to options and consequences. Peer Pressure can be defined as the mechanism through which peers influence each other to think and act in a certain peer accepted way. It occurred when individual experiences implied or

expressed persuasion to adopt similar values, beliefs, and goals and participate in the same activities as these in the peer group, Steinberg (2002).

Peers group by themselves may neither be positive nor negative. Studies by Jacobs and Gazel (1993) confirmed research findings that the values of the peer group with whom the high school student spends the most time with were a stronger factor in the students' level of academic success than the values, attitudes, and support provided by the family. Group composition often keeps changing in a growing child to adolescents when the child enters the middle school and have more opportunities to have new friends. Hartup (1990) reviewed evidence showing that adolescent initially associated with peers who resemble themselves in terms of behavioural interests and attitudes and subsequently reinforced in each those characteristics that brought them together in the first place. This leads to conventional friendship to further comply with social norms, whereas antisocial friends engage in increasingly problematic behaviour.

Regardless of Parental style, peer pressure can also influence the degree to which adolescents conform to expected gender roles. It is thus important to understand that these friends play in decisions about the attitudes and behaviour of adolescents (Coln, 1995).

Simons-Marten (2007) asserted that socialization occurs as a result of overt reactions of group members or through subtle, indirect pressure that is derived from group norms, expectations, social acceptance, and status. Kimmel and Weiner (1995) stated that socially, adolescents have a strong need to belong to a group with peer approval becoming more important as adult approval decrease in their search for self, model behaviour after older esteemed students or non-parents adults.

People with similar interest age group, back group, and social status form a part of a peer group. The study of the peer group is both a social peer group of like-minded and aesthetics group. The student's behavioral pattern happens in the schools wherein peers have a vital role in achieving such a change. Role of peer influence has direct or indirect influence in the academic achievement. Social and emotional development and education objective are influenced by the peer group (Alles 2005). Peers play an increasing role of influence from early age to teenage. Adolescents have a healthy relationship with their peers and give them importance as compared to other age group, and their trust in them is more pronounced, (Hardcastle 2002).

Table 4.1: Demographic Background of Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-22	43	43.9
23-26	55	56.1
Total	98	100.0
Gender		
Male	47	48.0
Female	51	52.0
Total	98	100.0
Living with Both Parents		
Yes	56	57.1
No	42	42.9
Total	98	100.0
Living with Father Alone		
Yes	10	23.8
No	32	76.2
Total	42	100
Living with Mother Alone		
Yes	18	56.3
Others	14	43.7
Total	32	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From the above table, the majority of the respondents are between the ages of 23-26 (56.1%) while 43.9% are between 18-22 years.

According to the table, 52% of the respondents making up the majority are females while 48% of them are males.

Table 4.1 shows that more than half of the respondents 57.1% live with both parents while 42.9% do not live with both parents.

According to the table above, 23.8% (10) of the respondents live with only their fathers.

It can also be seen from the table that 18(56.3%) of the respondents live with their mother's alone while 14(43.7%) of the respondents live with other people.

The totals for those living with their fathers and mothers alone are different from the total for the whole respondents. The difference in totals is because, some of the respondents live with both parents, so in this case, those respondents will not be captured in the totals of those living with their fathers and mothers alone.

Table 4.2: Social Influence

STATEMENT	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
I usually turn to my peers for information	23.5	19.4	28.6	16.3	12.2
Friends usually give me the advice i need	25.5	24.5	25.5	17.3	7.1
I am more at ease discussing my affairs with my friends	23.5	22.4	25.5	17.3	11.2
I get better insight into my sex life from friends	29.6	30.6	14.3	15.3	10.2
I discuss my inner conflict with friends	27.6	17.3	28.6	17.3	9.2
I enjoy the company of friends more than my parents	21.4	22.4	20.4	19.4	16.3
I can express myself freely with friends	9.2	10.2	19.4	27.6	33.7
I rather confide in a friend than a professional counsellor	37.8	20.4	22.4	13.3	6.1
Friends influence my life	52.0	19.4	15.3	8.2	5.1
I behave like friends do when I am with them	27.6	28.6	25.5	11.2	7.1
Peers influence my behaviour	45.9	24.5	15.3	8.2	6.1

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From the table 4.2, 23.5% of the respondents strongly disagree, and 19.4% also disagree that they usually turn to their peers for information while 16.3% of them agree that they usually turn to their peers for information. However, 28.6% of them are neutral as to turning to their peers for information. This shows that majority of the respondents disagree that they usually turn to their peers for information.

The table shows that 25.5% of the respondents strongly disagree that friends usually give them the advice they need, and 24.5% also disagree while 17.3% of the respondents agree to this statement. It can also be seen that 25.5% of the respondents are also neutral as to friends usually giving them the advice they need. This indicates that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that friends usually give them the advice they need.

23.5% of the respondents strongly disagree, and 22.4% also disagree that they are more at ease discussing their affairs with their friend's while 17.3% of them agree that they are more at ease discussing their affairs with their friends. However, 25.5% of them are neutral as to be more at ease discussing their affairs with their friends. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that they are more at ease discussing their affairs with their friends.

Table 4.2 shows that 30.6% of the respondents disagree that they get a better insight into their sex life from friends while 15.3% of them agree that they get a better insight into their sex life from friends. It can also be seen that 14.3% of them are neutral in this statement. This indicates that majority of the respondents disagree that they get a better insight into their sex life from friends.

The table indicates that 27.6% of the respondents strongly disagree and 17.3% also disagree that they discuss their inner conflict with friends while 17.3% of the respondents agree that they discuss their inner conflict with friends. However, 28.6% of them are neutral as to discussing their inner conflict with friends. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that they discuss their inner conflict with friends.

According to table 4.2, 22.4% of the respondents disagree that they enjoy the company of friends more than their parents' while 19.4% of them agree that they enjoy the company of friends more than their parents. It can also be observed that 20.4% of the respondents are neutral. It can be concluded that majority of the respondents disagree that they enjoy the company of friends more than their parents.

From table 4.2, 33.7% of the respondents strongly agree that they can express themselves freely with friends while 10.2% of them disagree that they can express themselves freely with friends. Meanwhile, 19.4% of them are neutral as to express themselves freely with friends. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly agree that they can express themselves freely with friends.

Table 4.2 shows that 37.8% of the respondents strongly disagree that they rather confide in a friend than a professional counsellor while 13.3% of the respondents agree that they rather confide in a friend than a professional counsellor. However, 22.4% of them are neutral. This indicates that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that they rather confide in a friend than a professional counsellor.

According to table 4.2, 52% of the respondents strongly disagree that friends influence their life while 8.2% of them agree that friends influence their life. We can again see that 15.3% of them are neutral as to friends influencing their life. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that friends influence their life.

From the table, 28.6% of the respondents disagree that they behave like friends do when their with them while 11.2% of the respondents agree that they behave like friends do when their with them. It can be observed that 25.5% of the respondents are neutral. It can, therefore, be concluded that majority of the respondents disagree that they behave like friends do when their with them.

From the table, 45.9% of the respondents strongly disagree that peers influence their behaviour while 8.2% of them agree that peers influence their behaviour. However, 15.3% of them are neutral as to their peers influencing their behaviour. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that peers influence their behaviour.

Table 4.3: Academic Influence

STATEMENT	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
The orientation for the first years prepared me well for the University	7.1	14.3	30.6	20.4	27.6
Group discussions give me a better understanding	6.1	7.1	12.2	28.6	45.9
I am able to discuss my difficulties with mates than in class	12.2	10.2	14.3	33.7	29.6

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The table 4.3 shows that 27.6% of the respondents strongly agree that the orientation for the first years prepared them well for the University and 20.4% also agree on while 14.3% of the respondents disagree, but 30.6% of them do not know whether the orientation for the first years prepared them well for the University. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly agree that the orientation for the first years prepared them well for the University.

From table 4.3 again, 45.9% of the respondents strongly agree that group discussions give them a better understanding while 7.1% of them disagree. However, 12.2% are uncertain whether group discussions give them a better understanding. It can be concluded that the majority of the respondent strongly agree that group discussions give them a better understanding.

Table 4.3 shows that 33.7% of the respondents agree that they are able to discuss difficulties with mates than in class while 12.2% of the respondents disagree, but 14.3% of them are not certain as to whether they are able to discuss difficulties with mates than in class. This shows that majority of the respondents agree that they are able to discuss difficulties with mates than in class.

Table 4.4: Emotional Influence

STATEMENT	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)
Friends influence my sex drive	55.1	21.4	12.2	8.2	3.1
Friends influenced my first sexual encounter	60.2	11.2	12.2	8.2	8.2
Friends contributed to my taking drugs/alcohol	64.3	13.3	10.2	4.1	8.2
I'm more comfortable discussing with friends about my erotic encounter	33.7	17.3	21.4	14.3	13.3
I got my first lessons with the opposite sex by friends	35.7	19.4	15.3	16.3	13.3
I would rather have a peer counsellor than a professional	40.8	12.2	21.4	8.2	17.3

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 4.4 shows that 55.1% of the respondents strongly disagree that friends influence their sex drive while 8.2% of them agree that friends influence their sex drive. However, 12.2% of them don't know whether friends influence their sex drive. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that friends influence their sex drive.

According to the table, 64.3% of respondents strongly disagree that friends influenced their first sexual encounter while 8.2% strongly agree with this statement. However, 12.2% are neutral with regards to being influenced by friends in their first sexual encounter. This indicates that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that friends influenced their first sexual encounter.

From table 4.4, 60.2% of respondents strongly disagree that friends contributed to their taking drugs/alcohol while 8.2% strongly agree that friends contributed to their taking drugs/alcohol. It can also be seen that 10.2% are neutral. This indicates that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that friends contributed to their taking drugs/alcohol.

Table 4.4 shows that 33.7% of respondents strongly disagree that they are more comfortable discussing with friends about their erotic encounter while 14.3% agree to this statement. However, 21.4% are neutral with regards to their being more comfortable discussing with friends about their erotic encounter. It can be concluded that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that they are more comfortable discussing with friends about their erotic encounter.

According to table 4.4, 35.7% of respondents strongly disagree they got their first lessons with the opposite sex by friends while 16.3% agree that they got their first lessons with the opposite sex by friends. It can again be observed that 15.3% are neutral in this statement. This shows that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that they got their first lessons with the opposite sex by friends.

Table 4.4 shows that 40.8% of respondents strongly disagree that they would rather have a peer counsellor than a professional while 17.3% strongly agree to this statement. However, 21.4% of the respondent chose to remain neutral. This indicates that majority of the respondents strongly disagree that they would rather have a peer counselor than a professional.

Conclusion

In conclusion, socially, peers are not influenced by way of advice or any sort of communication including their relationship and they are comfortable expressing themselves amongst their mates. The emotional effect is that peer pressure does not negatively affect their mood for an erotic encounter or seek comfort in drugs or other vices. Thus to an extent peers do not affect morality; thus whatever orientation they must have acquired in their growing period was self-developed. However, academically, peer influence is largely dominant as respondents overwhelmingly agreed that they are able to have effective group discussions outside the classroom and effectively discuss their academic difficulties. The fresher's orientation organized by the Institution settled them well into the institution. In effect by this study peer pressure cannot be considered a negative influence because generally students neither seek comfort nor find solace in their peers but rather can be used as an instrument of

academic excellence as students largely agree that they are able to have an easy academic discussion with their mates.

It can be deduced that peer pressure is a psychological phenomenon where one is prejudiced or otherwise depending on the personal orientation and it is not always a menace, and the academic institutions can play a major role in the orientation of the student as they found the fresher.'

Recommendations

The following recommendations are stated based on the conclusion of the study:

- The school authority should intensify efforts in making orientation for freshers quite effective and involve the students as it impacted well on them
- Since actively peers are influenced through group discussions of academic work authorities should consider students for academic mentors to encourage weak students
- The Guidance & Counselling Unit must incorporate academic peer counselling in their activities as students are more comfortable expressing their academic challenges with their mates.

Reference

- i. Berk, L. E. (2000). *Child development*.
- ii. Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development*. (1st ed). Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- iii. Kimmel, D. C., & Weiner, I. B. (1995). *Adolescence: a developmental transition* (2nd ed.). New York: Wiley.
- iv. Reason, J. (1990). *Human Error*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- v. Steinberg, L. (2002). *Adolescence*. (6th ed.). Boston, MA: McGraw Hill.